

Consent to Participate in Key Informant Interview – Ministry of Health

Background

Special Newborn Care Units (SNCU) are a critically important part of efforts to improve neonatal health in India. We are conducting a study in approximately 14 SNCUs and NICUs in the Vidarbha Region of Central India to understand the barriers, facilitators, gaps and needs in providing optimal care to newborns in the SNCU/NICU. This study, entitled “Best Bundles for Babies,” is being conducted by the Lata Medical Research Foundation, along with Boston University and Nexleaf Analytics.

Purpose

You are being asked to participate in this interview because of your expertise in shaping neonatal care policies. We would like to better understand your perspectives on the NICU sector and what influences the how neonatal care policy decisions are made for the best possible care for newborns.

What Happens in This Study

All or part of the research in this study will take place in India. If you agree to take part, you will participate in a one-one discussion with a researcher. The researcher will ask questions regarding barriers and facilitators to providing the best care to newborns. A second researcher will be present to take notes about what is said in the interview. We will also record the discussion on tape in order to make sure that we collect your information correctly. We expect that the discussion will take 60 minutes to complete.

Risks and Discomforts

The main risk of this study is that information discussed in the interview might be accidentally disclosed to someone outside of the interview. This might happen because someone overhears us talking or if a person not working on the study gains access to the recording of our conversation.

To reduce these risks, we will not collect any identifying information about you, such as your name or address. We will also not inform anyone about your involvement in this study. You may stop at any time during the interview and you may refuse to answer any questions. Our interview will be conducted in a private room. The recording of the interview will be kept on a password-protected computer and only people working on the study will have the password. No one else will be able to listen to the recording.

Potential Benefits

Your participation may help the investigators better understand how to strengthen care for neonates, including recommendations for SNCU/NICU equipment.

Subject Costs and Payments

There are no costs or payments to you for participating in this research study.

Confidentiality

Your participation in this study will remain confidential. No one but the researchers will be allowed to see your answers to the questions. While all efforts will be made to ensure confidentiality, confidentiality cannot be fully guaranteed. All the information that is written down and recorded will be stored in a

secure place. Information from this study may be used for research purposes and may be published, but your name will not be used.

Subject's Rights

You are 1 of 185 number of participants for this study. We anticipate that this interview will last approximately one hour. You can choose whether or not to participate in the interview and stop at any time. Although we will take notes on the interview, your responses will remain anonymous and no names will be mentioned in the report. You may get more information about your rights as a research participant or answers to other questions about this research by calling Dr. Archana Patel, Contact No. 0712 2249569.

Giving consent means that you have heard or read the information about this study and that you agree to participate. I am available to answer any questions you might have before you decide whether or not to participate.

Taking part in this study is voluntary. You have the right to refuse to take part in this study. If you decide to be in the study and then change your mind, you can withdraw from the research. Your participation is completely up to you.

If you choose to take part, you have the right to stop at any time. If there are any new findings during the study that may affect whether you want to continue to take part, you will be told about them as soon as possible.

Signed: _____

Signature of Witness: _____

Signature of Interviewer: _____

Date: _____

Place: _____